

NETWORKS OF CARBON NANOTUBES: HEALTH MONITORING OF FIBER COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

We have demonstrated that the integration of an electrically conducting network of carbon nanotubes in a glass fiber composite adds unique damage sensing functionality that can be utilized to track the nature and extent of microstructural damage.

Keywords: Carbon Nanotube Composites, Health Monitoring, Electrical Properties

ABSTRACT

The use of advanced fiber composites continues to expand in many structural applications. These composites are susceptible to the formation of micro-scale damage, such as interfacial debonding, matrix cracking, fiber breakage and delamination. The initiation of micro-scale damage has significant implications on the durability and performance of fiber composites. With the more frequent utilization of advanced fiber composites in primary structural applications there is a fundamental challenge to enhance reliability and performance while reducing maintenance. As a result there is broad scientific and technical interest in the development of techniques capable of monitoring the health of composite structures.

Developments in the production of nanostructured materials and composites with novel material properties have created opportunities where unique functionality can be added to existing material systems. Owing to their unique mechanical and physical properties measured at the nanoscale, the development of carbon nanotube-based composites has seen tremendous research activity over the past decade [1, 2]. As compared to traditional fibrous reinforcement, where the diameters are on the micron scale, carbon nanotubes are three orders of magnitude smaller. Due to their extremely small size, it is possible for carbon nanotubes to penetrate the matrix-rich regions of the composite around the fibers and between the plies of the composite. The formation of an electrically conductive network of nanotubes in the polymer matrix surrounding the fibers enables the nanotubes to be a distributed sensing network that can be utilized for sensing of deformation and damage *in situ*. As cracks propagate in the composite the conducting pathways are broken in the percolating network. The capability to sense damage is unique to nanostructured materials since a nano-scale conductor is necessary to sense the formation of a micro-sized crack [3, 4].

Figure 1: Optical micrograph (left) showing transverse microcracking in a cross-ply laminate and (right) graph showing the influence of transverse crack density on the damaged resistance and elastic modulus [5].

The graph in Figure 1 shows the crack density as measured by edge replication during cyclic loading and the damaged resistance, as defined in Ref [4]. There is an overall linear relationship between the formation of transverse cracks and the increase in the damaged relationship, showing that damaged resistance may be utilized as a quantitative measure of overall damage. The 90° degree ply becomes saturated with cracks near a crack density of 16 cm⁻¹. Even though the 90° ply is saturated with cracks there is a very small degradation in the elastic modulus of the laminate.

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References

1. E.T. Thostenson, Z.F Ren, T.W. Chou, *Composites Science and Technology*, 61 (13) 1899 (2001)
2. E.T. Thostenson, C.Y. Li, T.W. Chou, *Composites Science and Technology*, 65 (3-4) 491 (2005)
3. E.T. Thostenson, T.W. Chou, *Advanced Materials*, 18 (22) 2837 (2006)
4. E.T. Thostenson, T.W. Chou, *Nanotechnology*, 19 (21) 215713 (2008)
5. L. M. Gao, E. T. Thostenson, Z. G. Zhang, T.W. Chou, *Advanced Functional Materials*, in press.